

Original Research Article

Biotyping of *Candida albicans* isolated from the Student's Mobile Phones

Anam Aziz Jasim^{1*}, Taghreed Khudhur Mohammed², Hanaa N. Abdullah³, Ali Hafedh Abbas⁴,
Mohammed Abed Jwad⁵

Abstract

¹Lecture, Master biotechnology/Institute of Medical Technology/Al – Mansour/ Baghdad/ Iraq\ Middle Technical University

²Ph.D Microbiology/Institute of Medical Technology/Al-Mansour/Baghdad/ Middle Technical University

³Ph.D. Genetic Eng. and Biotechnology/College of Health and Medical Technology-Baghdad/ Middle Technical University

⁴Tropical-Biological Research Unit/ Science College/University of Baghdad/ Baghdad/ Iraq

⁵Al-Nosor University, Baghdad, Iraq.

*Corresponding Author's Email:
neamaziz73@gmail.com

Mobile phones are approximately widely used everywhere like in hospital wards, clinics, Universities and biomedical laboratories. It has become very important tool in students' life. In contrast, these tools carry many harmful bacteria and fungi which are responsible for infectious diseases in humans. This study was aimed to isolate fungi from students' mobile phones (MPs) and study the resistant to many antifungal agents. Also, know the appropriate remedial measures. Four hundred and fifty MPs samples were collected from four hundred and fifty students, their age range was (17 – 30) years. All swab samples were collected from students, then all swabs streaked on enriched and selective culture media to diagnose the fungi. From a total of four hundred and fifty swabs that were collected from the MPs of the students, 15 swabs (3.33%) showed positive culture for *Candida albicans* isolates. The percentage of isolated *Candida albicans* were 14 isolates (93.33%) in females' MPs and only one isolate (6.67%) in males' MPs was diagnosed. The results of the anti-fungal sensitivity of the 15th *Candida albicans* isolates were 100% sensitive for Amphotericin-B, Nystatin and Clotrimazole. While 100% resistant for Fluconazole, and Itraconazole, and the resistance percentage was 85.71% for Ketoconazole of females' MPs. The present findings concluded that the students' contaminated MPs could serve as reservoirs of fungal agents, and the close contact with these objects might play an important role transmitting the pathogenic microorganisms from person to other causing the diseases. Some *Candida albicans* isolates were 100% sensitive to many antifungal agents.

Keywords: Antifungal agents, *Candida albicans*, Contamination, Mobile phones

INTRODUCTION

The hands and mobile phones (MPs) of the students and faculty members in most universities around the world played an important role in diseases transporting. Many studies in Iraq and other countries showed that the MPs have a role in the transmission of pathogenic microorganisms. It has become an essential item in hospital wards, clinics, medical laboratories, Universities, even in operation rooms and toilet. So, has become a reservoir of the pathogenic microorganisms leading to

cause different diseases especially those associated with the skin (Ekraekene and Igeleke, 2007).

Many microorganisms are present on human skin, and digestive system as normal flora like *Candida albicans* (Hosseini et al., 2017). It is found in or on the human body without symptoms; the healthy peoples have >40% of *Candida albicans* in their oral cavities; and 20 – 25% of women have *Candida albicans* in vagina (Shahin-Jafari et al., 2016). Also, Hands act as a major route for trans-

mission of many pathogenic like bacteria, parasites, fungi and viruses, including intestinal species (Angelakis et al., 2014). *Candida albicans* may enter the blood vessels and reach kidneys, heart; brain causing urinary tract infections and meningoencephalitis. *Candida albicans* could be isolated from the MPs. So, MPs have become the essential items in students' life and it increased the spread of *Candida albicans* from person to another through contact or held close to the face especially in students' communities (Paterson, 2006; Mohammed et al., 2019). Therefore, this study was conducted to detect the fungal contamination of student's MPs in the Institute of Medical Technology/ Al- Mansour/The Middle Technical University (IMT/M/MTU), Baghdad, Iraq; and to study the resistance pattern to many antifungal agents to take the necessary recovery measures.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection

A collection of 450 swabs were collected from 450 student's MPs (271 swabs from male's phones, and 179 swabs from female's phones). The swabs were collected from the keys and covers of the students' MPs from the Pathologic Analysis, Medical Instrument, Pharmacology, Ophthalmology and Health Management departments at IMT/M/MTU/Baghdad/Iraq (Table 1). The samples were immediately transferred to the laboratory for culturing on an enriched and selective culture media.

Isolation and Identification of pathogenic fungi

The swabs were cultured immediately on Sabouraud's Dextrose Agar and Selective medium (CHROMagar™ *Candida*) which was used to detect *Candida albicans*. All culture media were incubated at 25°C and 37°C for 18-24 hrs. The diagnosis of pathogenic fungi was confirmed by observing the growth of colonial morphology of the isolates on enriched and selective culture media, biochemical tests was done by using API *Candida* system. In addition, the result was interpreted according to Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute guidelines (Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute, 2007).

Antibiotics Susceptibility Test

The anti-fungal resistance of *Candida albicans*

An anti-fungalsensitivity test was done on all *Candida albicans* isolates by using the disc diffusion method of Amphotericin-B (100Unit), Nystatin (100Unit), Fluconazole (25µg) and Itraconazole (10µg). Many colonies of *Candida albicans* isolates were mixed with sterile

0.85% NaCl₂. The turbidity was measured to equal a 0.5 MacFarland turbidity standard and then diluted 1:2 with a sterile saline solution. With a moistened sterile cotton swab, MHA surface was inoculated with *Candida albicans* isolates by streaking then allowed to dry for 10 min, and then antifungal discs were fixed on the surface of MHA with sterile forceps. All plates incubated at 25°C for 18 hr. The inhibition zones were measured in Millimeters (mm) by using a ruler and then the results compared with table 2 (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute, 2011).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The male's percentage of the 450 students was 60.22% (271) and 39.77% (179) for females. A total of 450 swabs were collected from the student's MPs of the five departments at the IMT/M/MTU. The current study showed that 3.33% (15 swabs) were *Candida albicans* isolates. The percentage of *Candida albicans* isolates was 93.33% (14 isolates) in females and 6.67% (1 isolate) in males; all isolates were isolated from mobile students of pathologic analysis department. As well as the apparent results have been noted that the most students were call their friends when they were in the toilet or when they worked at the Institute's laboratories during the training of microorganisms' isolation and diagnosis from clinical samples.

The present findings agreed with the results of Sweedan which demonstrated that the MPs bacterial contamination percentage was high as in the current study (Sweedan, 2015).

The results in table 3 showed that the antifungal susceptibility of fifth *Candida albicans* isolates. All isolates under study were 100% susceptible to Amphotericin-B (AP), Nystatin (NS) and Clotrimazole (CC). While it is 100% resistant for Fluconazole (FLC), and Itraconazole (IT), and the resistance percentage was 85.71% for Ketoconazole (KT) of females' MPs.

Although MPs are important tools of communication, but it has become dangerous tools in transmission of pathogenic microorganisms from person to others. The rate of isolated microorganisms from the students' MPs due to their contacts with the contaminated surfaces and environment. In the present study, the prevalence of *Candida albicans* might explain that the students deal directly with items in the laboratories then contact their MPs with the laboratory benches or even culture media containing pathogenic microorganisms through culturing or diagnosis. The MPs could become good tools for nosocomial infections in hospital units. Therefore, the proper decontamination of MPs devices by using 70% isopropyl alcohol is one approach which helps to reduce the risk of pathogenic microorganisms' transmission. Another study in Dammam (eastern KSA) referred that the percentage frequency of the isolated fungi was

Table 1. The collected swabs locations

Department	Male numbers(%)	Female numbers(%)	Total(%)
Pathologic analysis	120(44.28)	100(55.86)	220(48.88)
Medical instrument	65(23.98)	61(34.07)	126(28)
Pharmacology	46(16.97)	6(3.35)	52(11.55)
Ophthalmology	20(7.38)	10(5.68)	30(6.66)
Health management	20(7.38)	2(1.11)	22(4.88)
Total	271(100)	179(100)	450(100)

Table 2. Disc diffusion diameter of the isolated microorganism's sensitivity test

Antifungal agents	Sensitivity(mm)	Intermediate(mm)	Resistant(mm)
Amphotericin-B	>10	≤10	≤10
Nystatin	>10	≤10	≤10
Fluconazole	≥30	10–29	≤18
Itraconazole	=20	10–19	<10

mm = Millimeter

Table 3. The percentage of antifungal susceptibility of *Candidaalbicans* isolates

Antifungal agents	Positive MPs swabs No. (%)			
	Sex			
	Males		Females	
	Sensitive	Resistant	Sensitive	Resistant
Amphotericin-B	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	14 (100.0)	0 (0.0)
Nystatin	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	14 (100.0)	0 (0.0)
Fluconazole	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (14.28)	12 (85.71)
Ketoconazole	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (14.28)	12 (85.71)
Clotrimazole	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	14 (100.0)	0 (0.0)
Itraconazole	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	13 (92.85)	1 (7.17)

29.07% *Alternaria alternata* followed by 26.74% *Aspergillus niger* (Al-Abdalall, 2010).

Anibijuwon *et al.* reported that the source of contaminated bacteria on MPs may due to the normal flora that found on the human skin and hair, in addition to the fungi which transmitted by air and soil. Therefore, it is necessary to sterilize the hands after contact with a portable device to reduce the fungi transmission (Anibijuwon *et al.*, 2015). In Iraq, a similar study was done included 102MPs from the medical staff in Al-Yarmouk Teaching Hospital at Baghdad city, revealed that the percentage of *Candida spp.* Isolates was 5.88%. The researchers suggested that the sources of isolated fungi were might be from the human body as a normal flora or from the furniture and hospital items, or from air and soil (Shahin-Jafari *et al.*, 2016). So, it is must sterilize the hands after direct contact with MPs to decrease the probability of microorganisms' transmission by using 70% isopropyl alcohol (Corrin *et al.*, 2016). Finally, the present findings concluded that students' MPs were colonized with some *Candida albicans*, that these microorganisms might serve as a potential source of infection for students and other peoples. Therefore, it is important to wash the

hands carefully after using a MP, and the phone must clean with alcohol to reduce the transmission of pathogenic microorganisms.

CONCLUSIONS

The present findings concluded that the students' contaminated MPs could serve as reservoirs of fungal agents, and the close contact with these objects might play an important role transmitting the pathogenic microorganisms from person to other causing the diseases. Some *Candida albicans* isolates were 100% sensitive to many antifungal agents.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank all the specialists in the library of the Medical Technology Institute / Al-Mansour and all the students of the Medical Technology Laboratories Department, the Pharmacy Department and Ophthalmology and Health Management department for their

participation in taking samples and who supported my work in this way and helped me to obtain better quality results. I am also grateful to my colleagues with me in the current research for their patience and support for me in overcoming many obstacles that we faced. I would also like to thank my colleagues for their feedback, cooperation and, of course, their friendship.

REFERENCES

- Al-Abdalall AHA (2010). Isolation and identification of microbes associated with mobile phones in Dammam in eastern Saudi Arabia, *J Family Community Med.*, 17(1), 11–14.
- Angelakis E, Azhar EI, Bibi F, Yasir M, Al-Ghamdi AK, Ashshi AM, *et al.* (2014) Paper money and coins as potential vectors of transmissible disease. *Future Microbiol.*, 9, 249–261.
- Anibijuwon II, Odaibo DO, Omojasola PF, Ibrahim FR (2015). Isolation of Microorganisms on the Surface of Mobile. *Nig. J. Microbiol.* 28, 2821-2828.
- Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (2011). Performance standards for antimicrobial susceptibility testing, twenty-first informational supplement, 31(1), M100-S2. 2011.
- Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute (2007). Performance Standard for antimicrobial susceptibility testing: Seventeenth Informational supplements, 27 (1), M100-S17. Clinical laboratory standards institute, Wayne, IA, USA.
- Corrin T, Lin J, MacNaughton C, Mahato S, Rajendiran A (2016). The role of mobile communication devices in the spread of infections within a clinical setting. *EHR*, 59(2), 63-70.
- Ekrakene T, Igeleke CL. (2007). Micro-organisms associated with public mobile phones along Benin-sapele Express Way, Benin City, Edo State of Nigeria. *J Appl Sci Res.*, 3, 2009–2012.
- Hosseini Fard R, Hosseini Fard R, Moradi M, Hashemipour MA. (2017). Evaluation of the Cell Phone Microbial Contamination in Dental and Engineering Schools: Effect of Antibacterial Spray. *J Epidemiol Glob Health.* 2018 Dec; 8(3-4):143-148. doi: 10.2991/j.jegh.10.004.PMID: 30864755 Free PMC article.
- Mohammed TKh, Wahab Kh. M, Jawad MA (2019). Isolation and Identification of *Candida albicans* in different clinical samples, *Al-Nisour Journal for Medical Sciences*, 1(1), 85-97.
- Paterson DL (2006). Resistance in gram-negative bacteria: Enterobacteriaceae. *Ame. J. Infection Control*. 34(5), S20-S28.
- Shahin-Jafari A, Bayat M, Shahhosseiny MH, Tajik P, Roudbar-Mohammadi S. (2016), Effect of long-term exposure to mobile phone radiation on alpha-Int1 gene sequence of *Candida albicans*. *Saudi J Biol Sci.* 23(3):426-33. doi: 10.1016/j.sjbs.2015.05.001.
- Sweedan EG (2015). Isolation, Identification, and Determination of antimicrobial Susceptibility of Bacteria Isolated from Mobile Phones of Student, J. of University of Anbar for pure science, 9(3), 6-9.